

Adsorption and Desorption of Coen_2Cl_2 on Bentonite

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Adsorption and desorption studies of triethylenediamine cobaltic chloride on and from a bentonite clay show that adsorption is according to Langmuir's equation, and the desorbing cations arrange themselves according to the lyotrope series. Quaternary cations such as cetyltrimethylammonium (CTA^+) and cetylpyridinium (CP^+) ions desorb more strongly than the inorganic ions; CP^+ having a smaller cmc than CTA^+ is a more efficient desorbing ion. Both adsorption and desorption vary with pH and take place in stages. Thus, adsorption corresponding to maximum (95 me.) of Langmuir's isotherm occurs at pH 9.3; from pH 9.3 to 5.5, 15 me. more are adsorbed and again from 5.5 to 9.8 a further 19 me. are adsorbed. 95 me. corresponds to charge due to isomorphous replacement in the lattice and the latter two to what has been termed 'peripheral acidity'. Desorption studies with pH variation also indicate the existence of cations at the edges.

In recent years a considerable amount of work has been published on the systematic studies of cation exchange in pure clay minerals with inorganic^{1,2} and organic cations^{3,4} by a number of workers, but very little study on adsorption of inorganic trivalent complex cations⁵ by clay minerals has been reported so far. Our knowledge about the desorption of these trivalent ions from the clay complex is still meagre, the physico-chemical aspects of many of these reactions being still unknown in their fundamental details. It is in this context that an attempt has been made to study the sorption and desorption characteristics of triethylenediamine cobaltic chloride on bentonite.

EXPERIMENTAL

A bentonite fraction having particle size $\angle 2.0 \mu$ was isolated and collected by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation of Rajasthan bentonite (supplied by Calcutta Minerals Supply Co. Ltd.). It was converted into the H-form by resin (IR-120) and Dowex 2X-4 treatment and its b.e.c. was determined by titration with baryta in presence of 1M BaCl_2 solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. The value was found to be 100.0 m.e./100 gm.

The adsorption of triethylenediamine cobaltic chloride (Coen_2Cl_2) on H-bentonite was studied first. The pH of the solutions before and after the adsorption of the complex

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varied between 3.65 and 3.30. A definite amount of bentonite suspension was taken in a number of pyrex test tubes and different amounts of Coen_3Cl_3 were added, the mixtures shaken for two hours and kept overnight. The contents of the test tubes were then centrifuged (2000 r.p.m.) for 15 mins. or so, and the Coen_3Cl_3 concentration of the centrifugate was estimated from absorbance measurements using the Hilger Spekkar. The maximum adsorption of Coen_3^{+3} found by difference corresponds to 95 m.e./100 g. which agrees fairly well with the b.e.c. mentioned above. On the basis of this experiment the following procedure for adsorption at different pH was adopted. To mixtures of H-bentonite and Coen_3Cl_3 containing known amounts of each were added varying amounts of either HCl or NaOH in order to bring them to different pH values. The amounts of Coen_3Cl_3 adsorbed after equilibrium were then determined by absorbance measurements as above and plotted in Fig. 1 against the equilibrium pH of the mixtures.

FIG. 1

For studying desorption 10 ml portions of H-bentonite suspension (varying from 1.55 to 1.85%) were treated with the Coen_3Cl_3 in concentrations approximately two times the b.e.c. of the clay in a number of test tubes, to which varying amounts of different electrolytes were added. The upper limit of the final concentration of the electrolytes was kept about 0.3 *M*. The mixtures were shaken for two hours and allowed to equilibrate overnight, centrifuged for 15 mins. or so and the Coen_3Cl_3 content was estimated by means of absorbance measurement. Preliminary experiments showed that the same state of equilibrium was obtained if Coen_3^{+3} was adsorbed first and then desorbed with electrolytes, and hence the procedure described above was followed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The adsorption isotherm of Coen_3^{+3} on H-bentonite is shown in Fig. 2. The adsorption data are seen to fit into the Langmuir adsorption equation (Fig. 2). It is evident from the graph that no multilayer formation takes place in the range of concentration of Coen_3Cl_3 studied. The desorption isotherms are shown in Figs. 3, 4, & 5 and the calculated

Distribution and Selectivity Coefficients (see below) corresponding to a definite concentration of the desorbing electrolyte are given in Table 1. It is observed that compared to the quaternary ions the inorganic cations desorb Coen_2Cl_3 to a much smaller extent.

Adsorption isotherm of Coen_2Cl_3 on H-bentonite.
FIG. 2

Desorption isotherm of Coen_2Cl_3 by electrolytes.
From above : LiCl , NaCl , KCl , NH_4Cl , RbCl , $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$, CsCl .
FIG. 3

Cone. of electrolytes $\times 10M$
Desorption isotherm of Coen_3Cl_9 by
electrolytes.

From above : BaCl_2 , CaCl_2 , MgCl_2 .

FIG. 4

Desorption isotherm of Coen_3Cl_9 by CPCI (top)
CTA Br (bottom)

FIG. 5

TABLE I

Electrolyte used 1:1 electrolytes	Concentration of the electrolyte	Distribution coefficient	Selectivity coefficient
LiCl	$2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$	0.21	5.7×10^{-2}
NaCl	"	0.26	7.7×10^{-2}
KCl	"	0.47	1.4×10^{-1}
NH_4Cl	"	0.71	2.5×10^{-1}
RbCl	"	1.0	4.2×10^{-1}
CsCl	"	1.6	1.7
RbCl	$1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$	1.3	4.4×10^{-1}
CsCl	"	2.3	1.1
<i>2:1 electrolytes</i>			
Mg Cl_2	$1.2 \times 10^{-1} M$	0.44	1.8×10^{-1}
Ca Cl_2	"	0.57	2.2×10^{-1}
Ba Cl_2	"	0.72	2.6×10^{-1}
<i>Quaternary ammonium salts</i>			
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$	$1.2 \times 10^{-1} M$	2.1	9.9×10^{-1}
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$	$0.6 \times 10^{-1} M$	2.9	9.8×10^{-1}
CTA Br	$1.2 \times 10^{-1} M$	21	1.26×10^{-1}
CPCI	"	23	1.50×10^{-1}
CTA Br	$0.6 \times 10^{-1} M$	28	1.94×10^{-1}
CPCI	"	32	1.65×10^{-1}

The equilibrium may be denoted by

where the bar refers to the species in the clay phase. The Distribution Coefficient is

given by $\lambda_i = \frac{m_i}{\bar{m}_i}$, where $\bar{m}_i$ and m_i are respectively the molal concentrations of the species i and the Selectivity Coefficient is given by

$$K^i\text{Coen}_3 = \frac{[\bar{i}^{+z}]^{\frac{1}{z}} [\text{Coen}_3^{+3}]^{\frac{1}{3}}}{[\text{Coen}_3^{+3}]^{\frac{1}{3}} [\bar{i}^{+z}]^{\frac{1}{z}}}$$

where $+z$ is the valency of i .

It is to be noted that the values of the Selectivity Coefficients are in the order: $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{NH}_4^+ < \text{Rb}^+ < \text{Ca}^{2+}$ for the monovalent, and $\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+}$ for the bivalent and cetyltrimethylammonium ion (CTA^+) $<$ cetylpyridinium ion (CP^+) for the quaternary cations. The first two series conform to the lyotrope effect.

The desorption behaviour of the quaternary cations studied has been found to be of considerable interest. It is noted that they are 10 to 50 times more efficient than the inorganic cations. This may be due to their strong adsorbability⁶, geometrical relationship to the surface, surface-active properties³, and their stronger affinity for the altered clay surface³. The concentrations used of the quaternary electrolytes, it may be noted, exceed their critical micelle concentrations (cmc), so that the multiplied charged micelles are the actual desorbing species. CP^+ (cmc = $8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) is found to be more efficient than CTA^+ (cmc = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) because of its lower cmc.

The comparatively low efficiency of Na^+ to desorb Coen_3^{+3} is shown in Fig. 2. H^+ is known to have a higher exchange power than Na^+ . It is apparent from Fig. 1 that as the pH decreases below 2.5 the adsorption of Coen_3^{+3} also decreases, but above pH 3.3 the adsorption increases up to pH 9.8. It may be noted that the mixture of H-clay and Coen_3Cl_3 without addition of either acid or alkali has got pH = 3.3. Within the range of pH 3.0 to 9.8 two distinct stages of adsorption can be recognised: 95 to 110 m.e. (difference = 15 m.e.) and again from 110 to 123 m.e. (difference = 13 m.e.). The value of 95 m.e. probably corresponds to change due to isomorphous lattice replacement, or what has been termed 'internal acidity' as distinct from 'peripheral acidity' which refers to the last two stages mentioned above.

According to one point of view⁷ the stages correspond respectively to the adsorption at edges (15 m.e.) primarily caused by Si-O sites, and at the lateral surface (13 m.e.) constituted of Al-O adsorption sites. The other point of view has been expressed by Martin and Glaeser⁸ who observed similar stages of adsorption with hexamino-cobaltic chloride. According to them at high pH the adsorbate ions are no longer $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+}$ but may be $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ or $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{OH})_2]^{+}$ or both, depending on the pH. A similar postulation of $[\text{Coen}_3(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ or $(\text{Coen}_3)(\text{OH})_2^+$ may be made about the adsorbate ions at higher pH in the present case. Further work is necessary to ascertain the correct view. Furthermore, it is observed that Coen_3^{+3} adsorbed on the edges are less strongly held and are displaced more easily by H^+ ion. Fig. 6. gives the desorption curves of H- Coen_3 -bentonite and

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of Na-Coen₃-bentonite containing respectively 95 m.e./100g and 110 m.e./100g. respectively of Coen₃⁺. It is to be noted that in the Na-Coen₃ bentonite the desorption

Desorption of Coen₃Cl₂ from H-Coen₃-bentonite (bottom) and Na-Coen₃-bentonite (top) at different pH.

FIG. 6

begins at a higher pH (near about 4.0) and a small break appears at 10 m.e. corresponding to the desorption of the cations at the edges.

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